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SOME NOTES ON WORKING MEMORY IN COLLEGE-EDUCATED AND LOW-EDUCATED LEARNERS OF ENGLISH AS A SECOND LANGUAGE IN THE UNITED STATES.¹

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1 Introduction

This paper reports on some exploratory work that was carried out with educated and less-educated Spanish-speaking learners of English as a second language in western Pennsylvania and Ohio in 2006. The original intent was to compare working memory scores, proficiency, and sentence processing (especially of long-distance dependencies in relative clauses) among educated and less-educated learners. We intended to target speakers who had not attended university and those that had attended university. In hindsight, this project may have been overly ambitious in its conception, since we did not know the available pool of potential participants in the ‘less-educated’ category. This lack of knowledge turned out to be a major problem. However, we think that a brief report of our findings is worthwhile given the growing interest in this topic (Juffs, 2006; Tarone and Bigelow, 2005; and papers in van de Craats, Kurvers, and Young-Scholten, 2006). We therefore consider this paper to be ‘some notes’ that may assist others in future work, rather than a paper that presents reliable findings.

This report is structured as follows. First, we briefly review some definitions concerning levels of literacy. We then review Baddeley’s model of working memory and briefly mention Just and Carpenter’s (1996) constrained capacity reader model. We discuss how these models are operationalized in the second language (L2) literature, and raise some questions about such tests based on recent publications in neuropsychological assessment. We next sketch an original work plan and follow up with a description of two samples from typical populations from Spanish-speaking countries in the western mid-Atlantic region of the United States. We then report on our results. We conclude with some reflections on problems with carrying out working memory research with less-educated populations in our region of the United States.

2 Less-educated learners: a typology

The acquisition of second languages by less-educated learners has begun to attract increasing attention of scholars in both Europe and North America in recent years. This attention has arisen because less-educated migrants are affecting social and educational services in the destination countries (see Tarone & Bigelow, 2005 for some statistics and discussion of illiteracy). This population must be better understood if individuals are to be accommodated effectively in their new society. An effort is being made to pool knowledge about such learners through scholarly meetings and on line resources, see <http://www.lessla.org>. Knowledge of this population will also be

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important in developing a more comprehensive theory of second language acquisition (SLA), and may shed light on such controversial topics as the so-called ‘critical period’.

Participants at LESSLA symposia have suggested that less-educated learners are not a homogeneous group. Van de Craats et al. (2006) proposed a three-way split in less-educated learners to assist in thinking about this issue. The first group is totally illiterate, they have never attended school, and cannot read or write in *any* language. The second group, being low-literates, have attended some school and have a reading level below average primary school level in their first language (L1). The third subgroup are the ‘low-educated’, who have at most ten years of education in their home country and have also received a primary education in their L1. It was this last group that we sought to investigate, and to compare with highly literate university-educated learners.

The reason for investigating this latter group was to explore some of the cognitive, rather than cultural, reasons for their difficulties in achieving L2 oral proficiency. Such learners struggle to learn the L2 even when they receive instruction, and even when they are living in country. As is well-known, living in a country need not entail social ‘immersion’; see Schumann (1990). Moreover, they appear to learn more slowly than other adult learners and are more prone to ‘fossilization’ (Selinker, 1972) or getting stuck at a non-native-like plateau. Young-Scholten and Strom (2006) have suggested that phonemic awareness before formal instruction is not available to these learners in a way that is similar to L1 literacy development. In other words, although unschooled adult L2 learners may have a sense of word and syllable structure, they lack the ability to process at the level of the segment. This fact leads us to the question of whether individuals in this group who succeed have a greater ability to detect the segment and whether this is related to their phonological working memory.

The reason phonemic awareness may be related to phonological working memory is that individuals who have a greater working memory (WM) capacity may be able to hold words in memory longer for analysis of their phonological structure. Such an analysis facilitates the development of phonemic contrasts, which is necessary for developing vocabulary. In order to acquire new words, learners have to compare strings of sounds and distinguish which string matches which concept or concepts (e.g. Kroll and Sunderman, 2003). It is possible that the limitation on their WM never allows them to analyse the internal structure of a word; as a result, the word is lost from WM and never makes it into the long-term memory store to be compared with other similar strings and assigned as a label to the correct concept.

Our question, then, was whether phonological working memory is related to an individual’s potential to learn in instructed and uninstructed language learning contexts. This is certainly the claim in the L2 literature, (e.g. Ellis, 1996; 2001; Harrington and Sawyer, 1992), although results do not always support this strong conclusion (e.g. Juffs, 2004, 2005). The field has suffered from some confusion about the nature of the construct working memory and how it is operationalized and tested. Before turning to the empirical study and data that we were able to collect, we first summarize the models of working memory that we are assuming.

3 Models of working memory

3.1 Phonological short-term memory

Currently, working memory research in L2 distinguishes two kinds of ‘working memory’. However, the operationalization of working memory in the mainstream L2 literature does not always reflect advances in memory tests described in neuropsychological assessment manuals, e.g. Lezak et al. (2004). The type of test familiar to most L2 researchers is phonological short-term memory (PSM). PSM research is primarily associated with the British psychologist Alan Baddeley and his colleagues (Baddeley, 1999; Baddeley et al. 1998), who claim that variation in memory ability in PSM tests relate to language learning in children and adults. The capacity for short-term

memory has been operationalized in two different ways. The first test is of the ability to repeat nonsense words of different syllable lengths (e.g. 'landiplation', 'geplore') *accurately*; in some cases, syllable length can be up to nine syllables (Pappagno and Vallar, 1995; Gathercole, 2006). The nonsense words include sounds that are not in the first language of the child or adult learner. The version of the test with pseudo-words (i.e., non-words that contain unfamiliar sounds) is used to assess the ability to encode new phonological sequences; using non-words or unfamiliar strings of sounds prevents the participant from using stored knowledge to remember the list. Gathercole (2006) and the commentaries on her article reveal some significant disagreements with the model proposed to account for individual differences in the ability to repeat non-words and the relationship of these differences in word learning in children with specific language impairment (SLI). At issue is the positive effect of familiarity with substrings of phonemes in non-words that are similar to existing words. Overall, it seems that non-word repetition explains variation in early L1 and L2 learning, but that this 'primitive' learning mechanism is superseded by other factors such as auditory processes, phonological development, and output processes.

The second way phonological short-term memory is tested is by the ability to reliably remember lists of unrelated words in the same order as they were presented (Harrington and Sawyer, 1992; Just et al., 1996; Cheung, 1996). This measure involves the word *span* or digit *span* test. The presentation of the words can be either in written or aural mode. Variations exist on this model, but the basic idea is that individuals vary in their ability to remember lists of items in the same order as they are presented. There has been some confusion between the repetition *accuracy* task and the simple span task (Ben-Yehudah and Fiez, 2007). Differences in the method used to measure PSM may explain some discrepancies in how useful the tests are in predicting vocabulary size and language development (Cheung, 1996, p. 872), although some researchers report results that suggest that *both* measures tap the same underlying construct, namely PSM (Pappagno and Vallar, 1995, p. 104). In spite of these claims, some word span and digit span tests that require serial recollection in the same order are now considered to be tests of attention rather than working memory. Jefferies et al (2004) note that immediate serial recall tasks (ISR) are now considered to draw on many levels of representation and show effects of frequency, image ability and so on. In addition, digit span and word span appear to be preserved in different ways in semantic dementia, with digit recall being preserved where non-number words were not preserved. Moreover, depth of knowledge of the non-number words in the list assists in recall, showing that conceptual representation is important in recalling strings of words, with non-number words of high image ability, helping patients with semantic dementia in recall (c.f. De Groot and Poot (1997) on adult word recognition studies). Simple span tasks are thus not considered tests of memory unless a distracter task is used, such as in the Brown Peterson technique, described in Lesnik et al. (2004, pp. 416-419).

The construct of PSM is related to a larger model of memory, which is described and summarized in detail in Baddeley (2000). The model is provided in Figure 1. PSM is a measure of the phonological loop in Figure 1. The model contains other components that are related to PSM. The Central Executive directs attention – obviously one cannot remember something one has not paid attention to. This claim does not rule out 'subliminal noticing'; see Schmidt (1990). The visuo-spatial sketchpad relates to visual memory. An interesting more recent development is the addition of the 'episodic buffer' to the model. Although the construct 'episodic memory' is not new (see papers in Baddeley et al., 2002), the reason for this modification is that the episodic buffer may explain the behavior of individuals who have phonological loop deficits. These individuals fail or do very poorly on the tests that measure PSM and have difficulty with new memory/learning, but they can recall narratives and even groups of playing cards that have already passed in games such as contract bridge.

Figure 1. *Development of the Working Memory Model, Baddeley (2000).*

The body of research that claims to support the role of the phonological loop in language learning is extensive (e.g. Baddeley et al., 1998; Ben-Yahudah and Fiez, 2007; Ellis, 2001). The phonological loop has been implicated in the acquisition of *new* words in *children*, and does not reflect the knowledge that a child already has. Baddeley et al. (1998, p. 159, Table 1) report that in partial correlations for 3 year-olds, non-word repetition is more strongly correlated with vocabulary measures than digit span ($r=0.31$ vs. $r=0.16$ (ns)), whereas for 8 year-olds neither span correlates ($r=0.22$ (ns) vs. $r=0.23$ (ns)). In the data they report on for 13 year olds, simple digit span is related to vocabulary measures ($r= .46$, $p = .05$). One point to make here is that the values of r are not very high, e.g. $r=0.46$, which means that the memory test explains only a limited amount of the variance. (Of course, no matter what the value of r is, the test has to be statistically significant.) In addition, these ‘now you see it, now you don’t’ effects of different measures of PSM in L1 learning are, for some reason unclear to us, have *not* been given enough attention in L2 reviews of this literature until recently (but see Cheung, 1996; Gathercole, 2006; and Pappagno and Vallar, 1995). Baddeley et al. (1998, p. 167; Baddeley, 1999) also discuss research on *adults* which supports a role for the phonological loop in learning new words; however, this construct has not been implicated in studies of sentence processing or in the acquisition of complex morpho-syntax. Indeed, in the literature on specific language impairment (SLI), even the role of phonological storage as measured by non-word repetition has been called into question. Many of the same issues arise when considering individual differences in L2 development and should be considered in future work. (See commentaries on Gathercole (2006) that follow the lead article.) Before going into the role of PSM in L2 learning further, we turn briefly to reading span and working memory.

3.2 Reading Span and Working Memory

The Daneman and Carpenter (1980) working memory measure (RSM) is the foundation of a large literature in the research into the psychology of reading and comprehension for adults (see Conway et al. 2005). As far as we are aware, RSM measures have not been used to track first language *development* in children, probably because the task would be far too demanding, and because very young children cannot read (Ben-Yehudah and Fiez, 2007). Since the introduction of the test in 1980, Just, Carpenter and colleagues (Just et al., 1996) have developed the Constrained Capacity Model to explain individual differences in reading comprehension, speed and accuracy in resolving

ambiguous sentences (King and Just, 1991; MacDonald et al., 1992). The model also relates to differences in scores on standardized tests such as the American Scholastic Aptitude Test (SAT). The SAT is a test in the United States that assesses academic preparedness for university study (e.g. Daneman and Hannon, 2001). Their findings suggest that the higher one's RSM the better the scores on these tests. Since non-literate and low-literate learners obviously cannot deal with such tests, we do not discuss them further here.

4 Method

We originally planned a variety of tasks for the highly educated and less educated learners. However, the only data we were able to collect allow us to make some comparisons on individual differences in the non-word repetition task and proficiency in English as a second language. We therefore report only on those items for which we have data.

4.1 Participants

Participants were paid \$40 to participate in two sessions of about one hour. We tested 20 native speakers of Spanish who were in advanced degree programs or had completed at least a bachelor's level education. The educated learners were recruited from graduate students studying at the universities in Pittsburgh, were relatively easy to contact and were willing complete all parts of the study. Their biographical data are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. More Educated Participants, n=20

Participant #	Origin	Age	L1	Degree
1	Peru	30	Spanish	MA
2	Peru	52	Spanish	BA
3	Chile	28	Spanish	BA
4	Colombia	27	Spanish	PHD
5	Colombia	40	Spanish	MA
6	Honduras	46	Spanish	PHD
7	Peru	44	Spanish	MBA
8	Colombia	28	Spanish	PHD
9	Colombia	57	Spanish	MA
10	Colombia	67	Spanish	BA
11	Peru	31	Spanish	MA
31	Colombia	37	Spanish	BA
32	Chile	26	Spanish	BA
33	Venezuela	28	Spanish	MA
34	Colombia	28	Spanish	PHD
35	Venezuela	34	Spanish	MA
36	Honduras	38	Spanish	MA
37	Colombia	27	Spanish	MA
38	Venezuela	35	Spanish	MA
39	Colombia	30	Spanish	BA
Mean		36.65		
STD		11.37		

Attempts to recruit less-educated participants were more complex than simple recruiting on campus. The less-educated participants were sought out initially through personal contacts and through flyers distributed in restaurants in the city of Pittsburgh. In spite of numerous meetings, arrangements to meet, and phone calls, these attempts

were not successful, due in part to a crack down on undocumented immigrants in Pennsylvania. This fact is important for researchers to know when planning research with this population. We therefore turned to rural Ohio, where the possibility of recruiting informants was brought to our attention. A total of 16 participants agreed to participate in the study. Based on our screening criteria, including the requirement of some schooling in the home country, we eliminated two participants. Another two participants did not come to the second session owing to changes in work schedules. Their biographical data are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Less-educated Participants, n= 12 (out of 16 contacted).

Participant #	Origin	Age	Literacy In Spanish	School	L1	Years in USA
62	Mexico	40	Yes +	9	Spanish	16
63	Mexico	37	Yes -	7?	Spanish	25
65	Guatemala	24	No	5?	Dialect	1
66	Guatemala	31	Yes -	NA	Kanjobal	5
67	Guatemala	18	Yes -	2	Akateko	0+
68	Mexico	42	Yes +	9	Spanish	5
93	Guatemala	31	Yes +	4	Spanish	5
94	Guatemala	46	No	1	Kanjobal	1
95	Guatemala	NA	No	-	Kanjobal	3
96	Guatemala	23	Yes -	7	Ixil	0+
97	Guatemala	44	No	-	Ixil	1
98	Ecuador	41	Yes +	6	Spanish	4
Mean		34.2				
STD		9.47				

The most disconcerting ‘discovery’, as can be immediately observed from Table 2, was that not all the participants were, in fact, L1 Spanish speakers. Several of the participants spoke languages indigenous to Mexico and Guatemala in addition to some limited Spanish.

4.2 Measures

The participants completed the following tests and questionnaires.

4.2.1 Working memory test

The test of phonological short-term memory was part of the Comprehensive Test of Phonological Processing (CTOPP) (Wagner et al., 1999). This test has been normed over 1600 individuals from ages 5-24 in 30 US states, and has a test-re-test reliability of over 0.80. The CTOPP is designed to measure the capacity to store segments and their phonological detail; it predicts the ability to acquire new words. The phonological memory part of the battery contains three practice items, and 18 non-words from 1-6 syllables. Notice that the number of segments to be remembered is somewhat similar to a lexical list task. Example words to be repeated, transliterated here, are ‘jup’, ‘bajlidou**dg**e’, ‘wul**an**awup’ (bold face marks stress). The non-words are spoken by a female speaker. It is a non-word span task, which for the Spanish-speaking participants also contains segments such as the voiced palatal affricate that do not occur in Spanish. Participants listen to a recording of the ‘words’ and are asked to repeat them during a five second interval that occurs between each trial. Participants’ data were recorded on a DAT recorder and graded by three separate graders.

The CTOPP manual instructs raters to score the test as follows: 0 is given for any repetition that contained a segment that was either omitted, added, scrambled, or if the syllable stress was changed. Therefore, in the first instance, the original scoring

schema, based only on omission, substitution or switching, was used. However, if one applies 'strict' criteria to the repetition, such as if the segments were voiced or not, or whether the manner of articulation correct or not, e.g. /r/ vs. /l/, a different accuracy score is reached.

4.2.2 *Proficiency tests*

The proficiency test that was used was an old version of the Michigan Test of English Language Proficiency (Corrigan et al., 1978). This test is publicly available and reliable. Both groups were given the vocabulary, grammar, and reading sections, slightly edited for length and to remove some archaic vocabulary. The total possible score was 78. Obviously, it was also anticipated that this test would be comprehensible by both groups.

4.2.3 *Native language literacy*

Tarone and colleagues have reported on the role of literacy in oral proficiency development in a series of papers (Bigelow et al. 2006; Tarone and Bigelow, 2005). Briefly, they find that literacy increases uptake in oral recast tasks and conclude that literacy may facilitate L2 acquisition. Following their advice, for the less-educated learners we used a native language literacy screening device. We adapted the original Spanish language version of the University of the State of New York and New York State Education Department questionnaire. In this screening, participants answer the first three pages of questions by themselves (or with assistance if they cannot). Then they read short texts, and finally, for the participants who were able to answer the questionnaire on their own, they are asked to write a text similar to the ones that they read in a sort of 'parallel writing' task.

5 *Results*

5.1 *Participant recruitment*

As our less-educated learners came from all three categories mentioned at the start of this chapter (illiterate, low literate and less-educated) no measures that required full literacy in the L2 were possible. We were only able to collect data on the CTOPP and the Michigan proficiency instrument and some L1 literacy data.

5.2 *Results of working memory and proficiency tests.*

Descriptive statistics of the two groups' scores on the CTOPP and the Michigan are provided in Table 3. Scores from the two closest raters of the three were selected, with inter-rater reliability being $r=0.89$ for those two raters only. Since the highly educated learners were rated first, and we found a reliable correlation between proficiency and the strict score on the CTOPP, we only used the standard scoring for CTOPP for the less educated learners. This is because we were interested principally in the memory aspect, and not in sub-segmental features (voicing, manner of articulation) of phonemes.

Table 3. Michigan Scores and CTOPP scores.

Group	N	Michigan Mean(SD)	Mich. Range	CTOPP Original Mean(SD)	CTOPP Range	CTOPP strict Mean(SD)	CTOPP strict Range
Highly Educated	20	67.75 (9.24)	36 (41-77)	13.93 (2.15)	8.5 (9-17.5)	7.5 (3.03)	11.5 (2-13.5)
Less Educated	12	15.5 (8.42)	26 (6-32)	9.79 (1.41)	4 (8-12)	-----	-----

For the less-educated group, 8 out of 12 learners scored 9 points or above on the CTOPP, whereas the educated group differed with only 4 out of 20 scoring below 12. The relationship between the Michigan scores and the CTOPP was explored through correlation. These correlations are presented in Tables 4 and 5.

Table 4. Highly Educated Learners: Correlations between Michigan Scores and CTOPP

	Michigan	CTOPP Original	CTOPP Strict
Michigan Placement	---		
CTOPP Original	0.26 p=.27	-----	
CTOPP Strict	0.60 p=.005	0.74 p=.0001	-----

Table 5. Less-educated Learners: Correlations between Michigan Scores and CTOPP

	Michigan	CTOPP Original
Michigan Placement	---	
CTOPP Original	.27 p=.39	-----

Statistically, within the two groups, the relationship of scores on the CTOPP Original scoring to Michigan proficiency was weak and unreliable. Specifically, for the highly educated learners, the CTOPP original score's correlation with proficiency was weak and not significant, $r=0.26$, $p=0.27$. That is, if the scoring is based only on omission, substitution or switching. However, if one applies 'strict' criteria to the repetition, such as whether the segments were voiced or not, or whether the manner of articulation was correct, e.g. /r/ vs. /l/, then the correlation of CTOPP and proficiency for the advanced learners is moderately strong and reliable, $r=0.60$, $p\leq 0.005$. For the less-educated learners, the correlation was $r=0.27$, and not significant $p=0.39$. We therefore kept to the original scoring method for our next exploration of the data.

A reliable difference exists between the scores on the CTOPP by the less-educated group and the highly educated group, $t(1,30) = 5.93$, $p \leq 0.0001$. Naturally, the proficiency is also different, because the less-educated learners performed at floor and many did not even come close to finishing the test. (Obviously, a better test of proficiency for the low level learners needs to be found.) As a *purely speculative* move, given the reliable difference in the CTOPP results, we combined the two group's scores correlated performance on the CTOPP with ESL proficiency, using the ESL proficiency scores as a 'surrogate' measure for literacy as the 'predictor' variable. We found a positive correlation, correlation, $r=0.75$, (df, 32), $p=0.0001$. This relationship is linear, as illustrated in Figure 2, but as pointed out by an outside reviewer, it is possible that there are two data clouds that make this correlation spurious. We discuss this result further in section 6.

Erratum

Figure 2. Scatter plot of Michigan and CTOPP scores.

5.3 Literacy screening assessment

Figures 3 through 5 show some writing samples collected as part of this screening. Recall that the task was to write a text parallel to one they had read. The errors made are high lighted by circles and a rectangle. It is not clear how these samples might differ from samples from other, but similar, socio-economic status individuals in their countries of origin. More data need to be collected for comparison purposes.

yo quiero aprender ingles por que
 siento que es muy importante para mi
 por que estoy aqui en este pais para
 el trabajo para hacer amigas para todo
 se necesita aqui me siento unas veces
Mal na poder entender. Cuando alguien
 me dise algo y por eso quiero aser
 lo que este de mi parte ahora que
 ustedes me an dado esta oportunidad
 gracias

Figure 3. Participant 62, CTOPP Score 13, Proficiency score 13, L1 Spanish, residing in the USA for 16 years.

Participant 62's errors are remarkable in that this person was among the most active in the group, could drive a car, and had been in the US for a long time. It is possible that the errors derive from lack of print exposure, due possibly to a low level of literacy. If you cannot read well, you will not be heavily exposed to print. The evidence for this is

the lack of accent marks in very high frequency words: país 'country', aquí 'here', ingles 'English', esté 'be' -preterite verb. Many words are misspelled, e.g., *dise* for correct "dice" 'say', *aser* for "hacer" 'make', *an* for "han" 'have'-aux. There is also a lack of punctuation, e.g. *se necesita. Aquí me siento*. In addition, grammatically, this person has problems with the arguments of prepositions: '... *en este país para el trabajo*' 'in this country in order to work', instead of the correct infinitival complement, which is required by the preposition 'para': *en este país para trabajar*'.

From a formal writing point of view, this sample contains a run-on sentence, and around the 3rd line, it starts to get difficult to follow. The translation of the following segment would be broken up into 2 sentences in literate speech, but it is hard to tell exactly where, and even so is lacking somewhat in cohesion:

estoy en este país (I am in this country) *para el trabajo* (for work) *para hacer amigas* (to make friends) *para todo se necesita aquí* (for everything you need here) *me siento unas veces mal* (I feel sometimes bad) *no poder entender* (not being able to understand) *cuando alguien me dise algo* (when someone says something to me).

The writing of participant 63 in Figure 4 comes from a person who has resided in the USA for 25 years. In spite of this time, the level of English is very low. It is also clear from the L1 writing sample that Spanish also poses problems.

Para tener mejor Futuro
 ipara salir mas adelante
 y buscar mejores trabajos
 aquí en los estados unidos

Figure 4. Participant 63, CTOPP score 8, Proficiency score 10, L1 Spanish

Errors that may derive from a lack of print exposure include the conjunction "y" as "i" 'and'. In addition, it has been attached to the preposition *para* 'for' to form a single grapheme "ipara" when they should be separated as in "y para". There is also a lack of accent marks: *mas* instead of the correct *más* 'more', *aquí* instead of *aquí* 'here' which are both extremely frequent lexical items. Another interesting feature is the expression *salir adelante* 'go out', which is a formulaic expression that does not take an intensifier. Hence, it is odd to say *salir más adelante*. (One possibility that we cannot exclude for participants 62 and 63 is that they are not, in fact, *native* speakers of Spanish, even though they said they were.)

Figure 5 contains data from participant 66. There are orthographic mistakes in high frequency verbs like *hablar* 'to speak', without the "h" which is silent in Spanish.

Figure 5. Participant 66. CTOPP Score 10, Proficiency 32, L1 Kanjobal, length of residence 5 years

Second, agreement errors between noun and adjectives are evident: *amigos americano* (missing plural inflection on the adjective). There is also a lack of accent marks in words such as *inglés* 'English' and *más* 'more', but such errors may be common even among higher level SES speakers. Other grammatical errors include those in the verb conjugation paradigm, e.g., *aprendindo* instead of the correct *aprendiendo* 'learn'. Finally, there is an ungrammatical periphrastic construction with the verb *ir* 'to go': *voy aprendindo* instead of *ir aprendiendo*. The infinitive should be used instead.

To sum up, no matter the length of residence in the US or the L1, the writing samples from the less-educated group reveal the following characteristics. First, possibly due to lack of print exposure, there are no accent marks, no punctuation and there are frequent misspellings. Moreover, even among the Spanish L1 participants 62 and 63, we find perseveration, lack of embedding (recursion), presumably fossilized forms, and ungrammatical forms that show lack of control of agreement. The point is that the L1 literacy skills of the learners is low, and is reflected in their ability to write in that language, and possibly their ability to perform the non-word repetition task. Given these characteristics of L1 literacy achievement, it is not surprising that L2 proficiency is hard to attain.

6 Discussion

6.1 Participant recruitment

Participant recruitment was a major challenge for this study, and was not anticipated at the outset. The original goal was to recruit participants who had had some primary to secondary education and compare them to highly literate learners. Such a population is very hard to find in western Pennsylvania. It is possible that researchers may have more success in other areas of the USA where there are higher numbers of immigrants.

One of the issues that we encountered in rural Ohio was that the native language of the participants was not in fact the Spanish we had anticipated. It was probably due to our own ignorance of this labor pool that led to this surprise, and is certainly a cautionary tale. Table 6 provides some background on these languages, which have significant numbers of speakers and are morpho-syntactically very different from Spanish. Thus, for (naïve) US researchers, it is a reminder that an immigrant is from Latin America does not guarantee that that person knows Spanish (or Portuguese) or are literate in their L1.

Table 6. Profile of Indigenous Languages (All Mayan).³

Language	Speakers	Literacy
Akateko	48,500 speakers in Guatemala	5-10% of the population
VOS Word order	10,100 in Mexico, many refugees.	20% literate in Spanish
Kanjobal (Q'anjob'al)	77,700 speakers in Guatemala	5-10% of the population
VSO Word Order		26% literate in Spanish
Ixil	35,000 of Nebal dialect	10-30% of the population
VOS word order	18,000 of Chajul dialect Guatemala	10-30% literate in Spanish

On a social note, the numbers of Guatemalan indigenous people in the USA is due in part to civil violence in that country; 10,000 Akateko speakers (also known as 'western Kanjobal') are refugees in Mexico. The issue of 'Mexican' immigrants in the US media does not report on the characteristics of these migrant workers, nor do the media consider individuals' reasons for so-called 'economic' migration. In eastern Ohio and western Pennsylvania, it does appear that illiterate and low-literate migrants from Latin America are the norm. Perhaps low-educated people are more likely to survive in their home country or gravitate to larger urban centers in the US, where they can find better paying jobs. However, these comments are pure speculation at this point.

It is hard to say how many of the estimated twelve million undocumented immigrants currently in the USA are, in fact, members of indigenous groups in their home countries who are illiterate in their first language and only barely competent in their second language, Spanish. Citing census data, Tarone and Bigelow (2005) suggest that one third of 15-17 year old US immigrants are not literate in Spanish, so the levels among adults can only be guessed at. However, we can tentatively say that without (L1) literacy, oral proficiency in the L2 will be difficult to achieve because learners lack the ability to segment the new language and thus learn it. It would therefore seem imperative to address literacy in immigrant populations as early as possible if individuals are going to be able to crack the segmental code of the new language.

6.2 *Non-word repetition and Michigan proficiency*

We found that the method of scoring made an important difference with the CTOPP. The instructions for scoring this test make no reference to sub-phonemic features, but other work in SLA does, in fact, appear to score on phonological features. If a strict method is used for then the advanced learners, scores and proficiency correlate. However, it seems to us that this method of scoring transforms the CTOPP from a test of correct and full *order* of item/segments into a proficiency test of pronunciation. Given exposure to an L2, the advanced group can be more phonetically accurate. However, the test should reflect items' storage capacity and not sub-segmental phonological features. We do not know how many of the correlations that have been found with non-word repetition are of this nature, i.e. based on strict scoring of voicing and manner of articulation. If this is to be done, then researchers will need to be precise about how tests are scored and which phonetic features count as errors. For example, with /p, t, k/ in English, will scores that do not have [+SG] (aspiration) in syllable initial position be scored as wrong? It is not clear to us that requiring accuracy in phonological features is part of a memory test if, as Pappagno and Vallar (1995) suggest, all PSM tests, whether word, or digit, or non-word, assess the same underlying construct. (However, see Jefferies et al. 2004 and Lezak et al. 2004 for other opinions.)

³ Source: <http://www.ethnologue.com/> Retrieved July 21, 2008.

Clearly, if less-educated learners have a lower level of phonemic awareness because of their low level of literacy, they will do less well on tests such as CTOPP because they cannot track and store segments in PSM. It may be that literacy enables the high level learners to do the test better. Hence, it may be that literacy is related to ability on the phonological working memory test in ways that have not been suggested in earlier literature. In other words, frequency and intensity of exposure to text may enhance phonological STM. (See also Gathercole, 2006 and commentaries on that paper.) This is exactly opposite of the directionality of influence which is assumed in much of the SLA literature. This is a suggestion only, and it may not, in fact, be supported with more careful research because the data display in Figure 2 suggest two separate populations, rather than a gradual increase in literacy and working memory. It should also be noted of course that correlations are not an indicator of prediction or directionality of causation.

However, this result *does* recall work cited in Juffs (2006) and Tarone and Bigelow (2005), e.g. Petersson et al. (2000) and Kosmiris et al. (2004). It confirms some general conclusions noted by Tarone and Bigelow (2005, p. 84) on the role of literacy: “the acquisition of grapheme-phoneme correspondences in learning to read an alphabetic script, and also the acquisition of the abstract concept ‘word’ acquired in the process of learning to read, both provide important cognitive tools for the processing of oral language.” Our data hint at the fact that *low* levels of literacy, and not just *no* literacy at all, will also affect the ability to carry out a cognitive task at the level of the segment, and thus the ability to learn a second language. These data are also consistent with remarks in Bigelow et al. (2006).

To sum up, the CTOPP does not seem to be explaining variability *within* the less-educated or the highly educated learners, but it is possible that literacy of the higher group (as measured by their ESL scores) seems to be related performance on the PSM test, which requires an ability to recognize segments.

6.3 General discussion

The attempt to carry out some working memory research with less-educated learners in our region of the USA can not be described as successful. However, some hints that literacy provides access to segmental analysis comes through in the data, where we find that the highly literate learners do better on the PSM test, even though within the groups it is not related to L2 proficiency unless scored at a very fine grain of phonetic detail. A more important question concerns the direction of the relationship between working memory and literacy. Given that illiterates are obviously able to learn their first language, it cannot be that they lack the PSM to segment their L1 as young children. Hence, one might speculate that failure on a test of PSM by an adult would suggest that a neural change occurs which knocks out the ability to segment among illiterates and leads to failure in SLA. The advantage that literacy provides in SLA is that it overcomes a possible loss of ability in adulthood to parse the soundstream at the phonological level of segment, thus providing access to phonemic parsing necessary for language acquisition. Obviously, literacy is a conscious process. These results echo some comments made by DeKeyser (2000), who suggests that it is implicit learning ability that disappears with the critical period. We might speculate further here and suggest more specifically that the ability to process implicitly at the level of the phonological segment is what is lost. Hence, we agree with Tarone and Bigelow (2005) that the data from low literate learners are key for a fully developed theory of second language acquisition.

We also saw that low proficiency in English L2 was reflected in the low level of literacy in the L1. Participants 62 and 63, who had both been in the US over ten years at the time of testing, struggled to spell and write Spanish. They had also failed to learn English despite their participation in organized religion and ability to use some set

phrases. Comparative data from speakers in the home countries of the participants also needs to be collected.

7 Conclusion

This report constitutes some notes and speculative ideas based on a limited set of data and the existing literature. At best, it is a pilot study. Overall, we found that carrying out research on less-educated speakers in our region of the United States presents several challenges. It should be acknowledged that some of these challenges are due to our own lack of knowledge of this population, but their immigration status also presents severe problems for sampling and acquiring such knowledge without a long-term ethnographic study. With very good reason, potential participants are afraid of any official contact that could lead to deportation and the resultant break-up of families.

Second, differences in phonological working memory (measured as capacity to store segments) are not related to proficiency for the advanced speakers. (However, see Juffs and Rodríguez (2006) for discussion of Reading Span and proficiency.) This may be because the PSM tests phonological segmentation ability and language growth at very early stages. The advanced learners have passed beyond this stage. However, the non-word task was not related to the Michigan scores, possibly due to a restricted range of their scores in this test.

As noted, the less-educated speakers' scores do not reflect the amount of L2 exposure, and hence non-word repetition could be a reliable guide to language-independent (phonological) working memory in these populations. However, low-educated/illiterate learners performed poorly in the non-word repetition task when compared to highly educated learners. Although they are able to perform the task, the interaction with the 'testing' event and the equipment almost certainly means that the results would need to be normed for this population separately.

We feel that claims about the predictive nature of non-word repetition tasks for successful second language acquisition in general must be treated with caution due to problems with the stimuli and the scoring procedures used in most studies. Recall that the scoring may be based on the number of segments remembered, i.e. it is a string memory test and not necessarily a true span test given the important recent reviews of Lezak et al. (2004). Second language researchers need to distinguish clearly between a memory test and a test of phonological accuracy in voicing, place and manner of articulation, which is a proficiency test to some extent. SLA researchers in general should reconsider these issues and revisit some of the early literature on PSM to check how the non-word repetition tasks are being scored. As Gathercole (2006) and commentaries reveal, and the comments of an anonymous reviewer also suggest, there are many issues which the second language acquisition community need to be aware of before carrying out further research with span tests.

Finally, it is worth repeating our speculation that literacy may be the key to gaining oral language proficiency in a second language for less educated learners. The experience of participants 62 and 63 in their many years of 'immersion' in the USA may have been different if they had had greater literacy skills in their L1. We might speculate that text provides a parsing device that assists in noticing how the L2 sound stream might be broken up and analyzed for acquisition, compensating for the loss of implicit learning ability.

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